

Synthesis and Characterization of Cyclopropylcarbinol Derivatives of Some Elements

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Alcohol interchange technique has been employed to synthesize for the first time a number of cyclopropylcarbinol derivatives of different elements viz., B(III), Al(III), Ge(IV), Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Hf(IV), Nb(V), Ta(V), As(III), Sb(III), mono-, di-, and tri-butyltin(IV). These have been duly characterized by elemental analyses, ir, ¹H nmr and molecular weight measurements.

IN spite of considerable activity in the field of alkoxide chemistry during the last three decades^{1,2}, a survey of literature reveals that except two reports^{3,4}, no work has been carried out on the alkoxy derivatives of various metals with cyclic alcohols. In view of this, it was considered of interest to synthesize the alkoxide derivatives of cyclopropylcarbinol and compare their physical and chemical properties with those of alkoxides of acyclic alcohols.

Experimental

Stringent precautions were taken to exclude moisture from the reaction systems. Isopropoxides/ethoxides of B, Al, Ge, Ti, Zr, Hf, Nb, Ta, As, Sb and butyltin were synthesized by the reported methods¹. Benzene and isopropanol were dried by standard methods. Cyclopropylcarbinol⁵ was purified by distillation (b.p. 122°; lit. 122-24°) before use.

TABLE 1—CYCLOPROPYLCARBINOL DERIVATIVES OF SOME ELEMENTS

Reactant A g	Reactant B Cyclopropyl- carbinol g	Molar ratio A : B	Compound isolated and nature	% Yield (of dis- tilled/ sublimed product)	b. p. °C/mm	Analysis % ; Obsd./ (Calcd.)			Molecular weight Obsd. (Calcd.)
						Alcohol in azeo- trope g	Metal	OCH ₂ -C	
B(OEt) ₃ 2.77	4.11	1 : 3	B(OCH ₂ -C) ₃ Colourless liquid	91	88/3.0	2.49 (2.62)	4.89 (4.82)	95.0 (95.2)	241 (224)
Al(OPr ⁱ) ₃ 2.68	2.85	1 : 3	Al(OCH ₂ -C) ₃ Colourless highly viscous liquid	75	245/0.6	2.34 (2.37)	11.3 (11.2)	88.6 (88.8)	992 (240)
Ge(OPr ⁱ) ₄ 2.20	2.03	1 : 4	Ge(OCH ₂ -C) ₄ Colourless liquid	88	125/0.8	1.66 (1.71)	20.3 (20.3)	79.4 (79.7)	381 (357)
Ti(OPr ⁱ) ₄ 1.17	1.20	1 : 4	Ti(OCH ₂ -C) ₄ Colourless viscous liquid	80	156/0.5	0.99 (0.99)	14.4 (14.4)	85.4 (85.6)	511 (332)
Zr(OPr ⁱ) ₄ , Pr ⁱ OH 3.23	2.41	1 : 4	Zr(OCH ₂ -C) ₄ Colourless highly viscous liquid	98†	—	2.41 (2.50)	24.4 (24.3)	75.4 (75.7)	1224 (376)
Hf(OPr ⁱ) ₄ , Pr ⁱ OH 2.49	1.52	1 : 4	Hf(OCH ₂ -C) ₄ Colourless highly viscous liquid	20	Sublimed 290-300/0.5	1.56 (1.58)	38.8 (38.6)	61.1 (61.4)	—
Nb(OPr ⁱ) ₅ 1.90	1.77	1 : 5	Nb(OCH ₂ -C) ₅ Yellowish liquid	25	220/0.5	1.46 (1.47)	20.6 (20.7)	79.1 (79.3)	890 (448)
Ta(OPr ⁱ) ₅ 2.83	2.15	1 : 5	Ta(OCH ₂ -C) ₅ Yellowish liquid ‡	20	228/0.3	1.69 (1.78)	33.8 (33.7)	65.7 (66.3)	1056 (536)
As(OPr ⁱ) ₃ 2.20	1.91	1 : 3	As(OCH ₂ -C) ₃ Colourless liquid ‡	80	115/6.0	1.55 (1.59)	26.1 (26.0)	73.8 (74.0)	301 (288)
Sb(OPr ⁱ) ₃ 2.24	1.63	1 : 3	Sb(OCH ₂ -C) ₃ Colourless liquid --	85	118/1.5	1.32 (1.35)	36.3 (36.3)	63.2 (63.7)	360 (355)
Bu ₃ Sn(OPr ⁱ) 2.05	0.44	1 : 1	Bu ₃ Sn(OCH ₂ -C) Colourless liquid	75	108-10/0.5	0.31 (0.35)	32.8 (32.9)	19.4 (19.7)	376 (361)
Bu ₂ Sn(OPr ⁱ) ₂ 2.15	0.91	1 : 2	Bu ₂ Sn(OCH ₂ -C) ₂ Colourless liquid	50	138-40/0.5	0.69 (0.74)	31.5 (31.6)	38.1 (37.9)	369 (375)
BuSn(OPr ⁱ) ₃ 2.45	1.53	1 : 3	BuSn(OCH ₂ -C) ₃ Colourless liquid (on keeping changes to yellow)	99†‡	decom- posed at bath temp. 210/0.4	1.23 (1.25)	30.6 (30.5)	54.4 (54.8)	766 (389)

† Yield of undistilled product.

Boron was estimated as boric acid. Aluminium was analysed as oxinate. Arsenic and antimony were analysed by titration with standard solution of iodine. Other metals were analysed as oxides. Alcohols were estimated oxidimetrically⁶.

Infrared spectra of the products were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 spectrophotometer either as neat liquids or as nujol mulls in the range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} . A Varian A60 nuclear magnetic resonance spectrometer was used for recording ^1H

nmr spectra of the compounds in CDCl_3 or CCl_4 solution using tetramethylsilane as the internal standard. Molecular weight measurements were carried out with a semimicro ebulliometer (Gallenkamp) using thermistor sensor.

Reactions of metal alkoxides with cyclopropylcarbinol :

To a weighed amount of metal alkoxide (ethoxide or isopropoxide) in benzene (~ 60 ml) a stoichiometric amount of the cyclopropylcarbinol was added.

 TABLE 2— ^1H NMR AND IR SPECTRAL DATA OF CYCLOPROPYLCARBINOL DERIVATIVES OF SOME ELEMENTS

Compound	^1H NMR data (δ values)			IR absorption (cm^{-1})	
	a	b	c	(M-O)	(C-O)
$\text{HO}-\text{CH}_2^a-\text{CH}^b \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2^a \\ \text{CH}_2^a \end{cases}$	0.38	1.02	3.40	-	1030 b, vs
$\text{B} \left(\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases} \right)_3$	0.34	0.95	3.54	1370 vs, 1320 vs, 1270 s	1.05 m, 1065 m, 1030 vs
$\text{Al} \left(\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases} \right)_3$	0.36	1.07	3.64	610 vs, 570 sh, s	1140 s, 1030 vs
$\text{Ge} \left(\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases} \right)_4$	0.38	1.08	3.62	710 s, 695 s	1125 s, 1065 vs, 1030 vs
$\text{Ti} \left(\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases} \right)_4$	0.36	1.18	4.09	630 b, vs	1120-980 b, vs
$\text{Zr} \left(\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases} \right)_4$	0.50	1.26	4.00	645 m, 595 s, 500 m	1120 vs, 1030 vs
$\text{Hf} \left(\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases} \right)_4$	0.32	1.20	3.90	620 m	1135 b, s, 1060 s, 1030 s
$\text{Nb} \left(\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases} \right)_5$	0.35	1.10	4.26	645 vs, 615 s	1165 s, 1090 vs, 1060 vs
$\text{Ta} \left(\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases} \right)_5$	0.35	1.08	4.23	600 vs, 535 s	1130-1000 b, vs
$\text{As} \left(\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases} \right)_3$	-	-	-	660 vs, 625 sh	1170 s, 1135 s, 1110 s, 1030 vs
$\text{Sb} \left(\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases} \right)_3$	0.43	1.09	3.80	630 m, 615 m	1170 vw, 1120 w, 1100 w, 1030 vs
$\text{Bu}_3\text{Sn} \left(\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases} \right)_3$	No fine structure		3.44	650 s, 600 m, 510 m	1125 w, 1060 vs, 1040 vs
$\text{Bu}_4\text{Sn} \left(\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases} \right)_3$	Due to butyl group		3.48	655 s, 605 s, 525 s	1130 m, 1060 vs, 1040 vs
$\text{BuSn} \left(\text{OCH}_2-\text{CH} \begin{cases} \text{CH}_2 \\ \text{CH}_2 \end{cases} \right)_3$			3.42	600 vs, 525 vs	1085-960 b, vs

vs = very strong, s = strong, m = medium, w = weak, vw = very weak, sh = shoulder and b = broad.

The reaction mixture was refluxed with a fractionating column and the alcohol (ethanol or isopropanol) liberated was fractionated out azeotropically with benzene. The excess of solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the product was finally dried at $\sim 50^\circ/10$ mm. Other synthetic details and analytical data are summarized in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The method of synthesis chosen was to treat the ethoxide or isopropoxide of the metal (or butyltin) with cyclopropylcarbinol (in the required stoichiometric ratio) in benzene. The alcohol liberated in the reaction was fractionated out azeotropically with benzene. The progress of the reaction was followed by the estimation⁶ of the liberated alcohol by an oxidimetric method using *N* potassium dichromate in 12.5% sulphuric acid. The reactions can be represented by the following equations :

(where M=B, Al, As or Sb ; n=3,
M=Ge, Ti, Zr or Hf ; n=4,
M=Nb or Ta ; n=5,
and R=Et or *i*-Pr)

(where n=1, 2 or 3)

The reactions are rather slow and take a long time for completion (about 6 to 8 hr). The slow nature of the reaction could be attributed to steric factors which appear to be more effective in the case of cyclopropylcarbinol in comparison to similar acyclic alcohols.

All the new alkoxides are found to be colourless (or yellowish in some cases) liquids. They are soluble in common organic solvents. Except zirconium and monobutyltin derivatives, others could either be distilled or sublimed under reduced pressure in quantitative yields.

Variations similar to those in the corresponding acyclic alcohols have been observed in the degrees of molecular association of these newly synthesized

alkoxides of cyclopropylcarbinol; thus while alkoxides of boron, germanium, arsenic, antimony, di- and tributyltin are monomeric in solution, the alkoxides of aluminium, titanium, zirconium, niobium, tantalum and monobutyltin exhibit molecular association (i.e. dimer to tetramer).

A broad band in the region 3350 cm^{-1} due to intramolecularly hydrogen bonded OH group in cyclopropylcarbinol⁷ disappears in the infrared spectra of the compounds indicating the formation of M-O bond. A shifting towards higher frequency of C-O stretching mode as compared to the parent alcohol has been observed in the spectra of these compounds. The M-O stretching frequencies in these alkoxides also appear in the same regions which are characteristic of metal alkoxides in general for a specific metal.

In the ^1H nmr spectra, hydroxylic proton resonance in the parent alcohol⁸ at $\delta=2.65$ ppm does not appear in the spectra of these compounds indicating the formation of M-O bond. The resonances due to acyclic methylene protons have been found to be deshielded in these compounds compared to the cyclopropylcarbinol. ^1H NMR and ir spectral data are summarised in Table 2.

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References

1. D. C. BRADLEY, R. C. MEHROTRA and D. P. GAUR, "Metal Alkoxides", Academic Press, London, 1978.
2. S. C. GOEL, Ph.D. Thesis, University of Delhi, 1979.
3. C. GOPINATHAN and J. GUPTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 948.
4. A. N. NESMEYANOV, "Selected Works in Organic Chemistry", Pergamon Press, London, 1963, p. 816.
5. N. J. DEMJANOV and K. FORTUNATOV, *Ber.*, 1907, 40, 4397.
6. R. C. MEHROTRA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 31, 904.
7. L. JORIS, P. R. SCHLEYER and R. GLEITER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 90, 327.
8. A. ABRAHAMS, S. E. WEBERLEY and F. C. NACHOD, *Appl. Spectrosc.*, 1964, 18, 13.